

StringScore: Composing Music with Visual Text

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces *StringScore*, a productive text-based Music Representation for Composition that provides a visual arrangement of motivic elements in a compact and meaningful layout of characters. Time dimension is represented horizontally, taking the text character as the time unit, thus considering character strings as time-lines where musical elements are sequenced. While being compact, *StringScore* provides a high degree of independent control of the fundamentals of traditional composition, such as musical form, harmony, melodic contour, texture and counterpoint. The description of the proposed representation has been illustrated with musical examples of applied composition. As an additional validation, *StringScore* has been successfully applied in the analysis and re-composition of the beginning of *Beethoven's Fifth Symphony*. Finally, the paper presents “*StringScore in the Cloud*”, a Web-based implementation that probes the representation in the environment of the *Computer Music Cloud*.

1. INTRODUCTION

This proposal addresses the challenge of music composition using a text-based representation that facilitates the arrangement of motivic elements in *time*, keeping control of musical form, harmony and texture, as well as providing a visual feedback of the arrangement, in a compact and musically-semantic textual form. This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the context of the proposal. *StringScore*, the proposed Music Representation, is described in Section 3, incorporating examples of musical composition. Section 4 checks the representativity of *StringScore* under the approach of Musical Analysis, by re-composing the beginning of *Beethoven's Fifth Symphony* from its analysis in *StringScore* format. Section 5 checks the representation in a Web-based application, *StringScore in the Cloud*, describing the prototype implementation as a *Computer Music Cloud*. The paper ends with some conclusions in Section 6.

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2. CONTEXT

This section reviews some aspects of the context where our proposal arises. Firstly, a brief survey about text-based music representations is introduced as well as the motivation to explore the visual representation capabilities of text. Secondly, we present the traditional composition model based in motives, on which *StringScore* is based. Finally, two related works in the context of our research are briefly introduced, such as *EvMusic Representation* and the *Computer Music Cloud*.

2.1 Text-Based Music Representation

Many of the Music Representations proposed by different musical systems along the history of Computer Music, are textual representations. For example, the score in Csound [1] and other descendants of *Music V*, is essentially a text file [2]. In general textual representation offers many advantages over the binary representation [3]. Particularly in music, the textual format is preferred because it facilitates readability and the data exchange between applications. Some text formats aiming to encoding of music notation have been reported [4–8]. Above this performance-level, composition elements of a higher level of abstraction have been described directly in textual programming languages such as LISP, as in *Common Music/Grace* [9] or *Open Music* [10], and other specific languages [11–13].

Despite of their capability of representation of highly abstract musical entities, provided by encapsulation and an *Object-Oriented* approach, their text format lacks some visual information, derived from the position of characters inside the text block. At the opposite extreme, there are those detailed pictures drawn with text-characters, a text format containing rich visual information but no text semantics. The motivation of our proposal is to combine musical semantics with some visual representativity in musical time.

In this sense, some text-based representations are of special interest. Those using one of the paper dimensions to represent the musical time conforming a Cartesian topology. As an example, in ***kern*, the music representation of *Humdrum* [14], the music canvas is arranged in a *time vs instrumental part* disposition. This is the opposite to the traditional *instrumental part vs time* disposition found in a conventional score, but it avoids line breaks.

The introduction of graphical interfaces for the creation and edition of music, have provided important advantages in operation, specially in the management of musical time.

However, the challenge of our proposal is to explore visual capabilities of the musical arrangement without sacrificing the benefits of text format, specially valuable in the Web environment. A focus is applied to the visual representation of those symbolic entities involved in the motive-based composition model.

2.2 Schoenberg's Motive Composition Model

In *The Gedanke manuscripts* [15], Arnold Schoenberg describes music composition as a structure of small elemental units called *motives*, “the smallest part of a musical piece with self identity”. In the music piece, motives can be presented in a simple form, ornamented form or as a transformation, but it can be recognized whenever it appears regardless of variation or transformation. Schoenberg also describes the concept of motive features or “marks of the motive”. “They are indeed primarily of a purely musical nature: pitches (intervals), rhythm, harmony, contrapuntal combination, stress and possibly dynamics”. As mentioned, one of the main motive features is *pitch*. It is important to observe that Schoenberg describes two features for an unique absolute pitch dimension. He differentiates between pitch feature and harmony feature. The first feature refers to the motive shape or interval, with independence of harmony or scale, the second feature. Under this approach, the composition space can be shown as a Cartesian canvas with *time* as horizontal dimension, and where motives are arranged like in a painting process.

Although some systems implementing aspects of this model have been reported like *Hyperscore*¹ and *OM Maquette* [10], they are based on graphic tools. As mentioned, our proposal aims to represent motive-based composition in a visual text format. This composition model is even expanded by incorporating dynamic parameters and motives, the development of *Symbolic Pitch*, and the use of motive segments as composition blocks. Some of these new features are inherited directly from our Representation *EvMusic*.

2.3 EvMusic: A Solid Representation for Music Composition

The extension of the motive-based composition model is inspired by Biology and the dynamic character of life. In this sense, the principle that “Everything in Nature is evolving” have been taken as a solid foundation. It is then transformed into “Everything in Music is evolving” and “No one is a constant”. Not only these principles have inspired the composition model proposed, but they have guided the design of *EvMetamodel* [16], the core of *EvMusic*, the representation over which *StringScore* is developed. *EvMusic* is a robust music representation endowed with high multi-level representativity, multiple topologies and a meticulous and detailed treatment of musical pitch, as well as full compatibility with the traditional music notation. Likewise, its multi-level nature and its expandability allow the representation of music elements at varied abstraction levels. It also supports the modeling of diverse music composition

procedures. Under the scope of this composition model, two main qualities of *EvMusic* are of special relevance. In one hand, its *evolution* feature assures that every parameter is never a constant, but a *Dynamic object*. Every object-definition is a set of evolving parameters that are sampled at the event-time that the object is required to manifest. This is a very valuable feature for modeling composition procedures based on dynamic behaviors.

On the other hand, *EvMusic* features an exquisite representation of the musical *pitch* dimension in a wide range of symbolic forms like *pitchnumber*, *pitchclass*, *scale degree*, *interval*, *chord*, *scale* or *tonality*. It solves pending issues like pitch spelling and successfully deals with pitch-related questions like *diatonicity*, *harmonization* or *densification*. Combined with the rich management of the time dimension provided by the *Ev Metamodel*, it can represent any type of musical symbolic event including *dynamic motives*.

2.4 Computer Music Cloud (CMC)

The development of Information Technology has provided a new paradigm for Computer Music. In the *Computer Music Cloud* (CMC) approach [17] the music system is distributed across specialized services on-line. The user interface is now a Web application running in a standard browser. A storage service is used as an edition memory. An intelligent-dedicated service is allocated for music calculation and development. Output formats such as MIDI, graphic score and sound file are rendered by independent services exclusively devoted to this task. The web application includes user-related features and assign storage services for the session. The key factor in successful integration is the use of a well-defined music representation for music data interchange: MusicJSON [13].

The CMC approach has several advantages. Some of them come from Cloud Computing, such as scalability, optimization and reuse of available resources. Others come from Web applications, such as decentralized information, being able to work from any computer with a standard Internet connection and browser, and the inherited code. Also, the division of the music system into services allows for the design and implementation of independent services with the most appropriate tools. Since services are available for different CMCs, the design of new music systems is facilitated by the joint work of available services.

As mentioned, one of the reasons for exploring the potential of text format is its suitability for this Cloud environment. In Section 5 *StringScore*, the proposed representation, is checked in a Web-based application, *StringScore in the Cloud*. The design and implementation of the prototype as a Computer Music Cloud is also described.

3. STRINGSCORE REPRESENTATION

The main drawback to address in text-based music representations, is the lack of visual representativity of time dimension and its management. Visualizing time is an essential requirement in predictive composition of music. After all, music is the organization of sounds in time. In addition to the sequencing of events in a single timeline, in the

¹ <http://www.hyperscore.com/>

```

(defparameter ritmo "*-+-+ *--+- *-+*-+*-+- ")
(def-motives-table2
  c '(a d f g c b e -b) "*-+-+ +-+-+ *----- *-----"
  f '( a ) (acentos ritmo))
(setf mc (densify mc $((0d a) (4d a))))
(define-pcs-name "modo1" '(0 4 7 13) :type 'scale)
(define-pcs-name "modo2" '(0 4 7 10) :type 'scale)
(def-section-stringscore variacion-3a
  1/8 tp 220 mt "6/8"
  dy "p
; |-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|
; "1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 "
sc "a b a b a b a b a b a b a b a b c d "
'( emodo1 fmodo2 gmodo1 abmodo2 )
e4 sk sa4
mo " " " " " " " " " " " "
e1 sk sc4
mo " " " " " " " " " " " "
e2 sk sd#3
mo " " " " " " " " " " " "
e3 sk sf#2
mo " " " " " " " " " " " "
e5 sk sd3
mo " " " " " " " " " " " "
(list :f (densify mf $((0d a) (4d a) (7d a) (13d a) )))
)

```

Figure 1. Excerpt of code containing the definition of a music section, in a preliminary version (2001) of *StringScore* format, corresponding to the piece for orchestra “*Camino Iniciático*” [18] (shown in Fig. 2). The original code has been cut vertically in order to accommodate the column width of this paper

composition process, it is also important to visualize the relationships that occur among the different timelines that comprises a music section.

This is particularly important in the motive-based model, where a flexible placement in time of the motives, according to the temporal position of the motives in other tracks, is required, as well as managing synchronicity with global continuous parameters of music such as harmony and dynamics. In this section we introduce *StringScore*, as the result of a long period of research and exploration of the representation capabilities of text, as visual time, in applied composition. Before getting into the details, a preliminary example of *StringScore* is presented as introductory overview.

3.1 A Preliminary Example of *StringScore*

Throughout our research, character *strings* have been used for this purpose for long. Some preliminary versions of *StringScore* have been tested in real music compositions. As an introductory overview of *StringScore*, Figure 1 shows a fragment of LISP code including the definition of a music section, in a preliminary version (2001), for the piece “*Camino Iniciático*” [18] for orchestra. The corresponding graphic notation is shown in Figure 2 as illustration and comparison to the code.

First line in Figure 1 is the definition of the rhythm *ritmo* as a string, within the character meaning shown in Figure 3. Following, motives *c* and *f* are initially defined. The rhythm for motive *f* is the extraction of accents from the given rhythm *ritmo*. Both motives are expanded in *pitch* by using the *densify* function with an expansion vector. In

Figure 2. Excerpt from “*Camino Iniciático*” [18] corresponding to the example code in Fig. 1

motive *c* (bound to the lisp symbol *mc*), the vector indicates two voices in diatonic thirds, as can be observed in Figure 2. In motive *f* pitch densification is indicated in the last line using a four-voices vector (third, fifth and ninth) of diatonic intervals. After defining two new types of musical scale to be used (*modo1* and *modo2*), the rest of the code is the definition of a music section by the arrangement of motives *c* and *f* over a Cartesian canvas in a *track vs time* disposition. Please observe the visual correlation of the instrument participation when compared to the notated result in Figure 2. This example is an implementation of the Schoenberg’s model where pitches are treated as *scale degrees* symbols distributed in the section. The vertical harmony (defined at the line starting with the label “*sc*”) is imposed to the symbolic pitches as a harmonization constraint, then the real pitches are obtained.

The representation introduced in this paper as *StringScore* is an evolution of the representation shown in the example of the Figure 1, but implementing our *Biologic Music* composition model as an extension of the motive-based one, and incorporating the basis of the representation *EvMusic*.

3.2 Character as the Horizontal Time Unit

In *StringScore*, character sequences or *strings*, are used as time lines where events can be placed. The unit of time dimension is the text character. There is a compromise to fulfill between time specification and semantic readability, so several models are proposed. Depending on the type of the musical element and its magnitude, the most appropriate model is chosen. In following subsections some string models are explained ranging from the representation of rhythms to the definition of whole music sections based in motives.

Character	Meaning
+	normal note start
-	prolongate duration
*	accented note
,	silence
Space	ignored
	measure bar (ignored)
(tie start
)	tie end
[tuplet start
]	tuplet end
numeric char	tuplet type (After)
i,s	staccato
V	strong accent
'	staccatissimo
t,m	marcato
j	accented staccato

Figure 3. StringScore: Characters used in the definition of Rhythm and Articulation

3.3 Motive Definition

The example in Figure 1 shown how strings can define rhythms and motives. It is a quick way to even define articulated figures by using different characters. Figure 3 shows the proposed meaning for the set of characters involved in rhythmic figures. An example including articulation, is shown in [Line 4 in Figure 5], and its notated result in bars 1 and 2 of Figure 6. Pitches can be defined in several ways, but they are treated symbolically according to *EvMusic*.

3.4 Track Definition

As an expansion of the Schoenberg's model, the building block for instrumental tracks in *EvMusic* is the entity *segment*. Segments constitute the participation of thematic motifs in the piece. Basically, they are portions of a motive, on which different motivic transformations such as transposition, inversion, augmentation or retrograded have been applied. Accordingly, the instrumental track is represented by a string containing some segment descriptors between space characters representing silence [see lines 20 and 21 in Figure 5]. The structure of every segment descriptor is of the form:

```
[pointer][+][transformation].[duration|mute].[sustain].+
```

The segment descriptor usually starts with a lowercase character used as a pointer to the motive to be sampled. Alternatively it can start with "+" indicating to go back to the beginning of the last pointed motive. Following, one or more characters describe the transformations to be applied to the pointed motive. They can be uppercase characters, usually with semantic meaning, or pointers to new functions. Also a numeric character, optionally preceded by "_", can be used to indicate pitch transposition. Transformation characters can also be used as *role* pointers, an advanced feature that assigns a role inside the counterpoint texture. The dash (-) character is used to complete the duration of the segment. In no pointer nor transformation is found, the dash character in the head of the descriptor, indicates that the last motive will continue during the seg-

Character	Meaning
lower char	motive pointer
+	beginning of the last motive
upper char	transformation (except M)
I	inversion
R	retrogradation
A	augmentation
D	diminution
numeric char	transposition (optionally preceded by _)
-	prolongate duration
M	mute
=	sustain
Space	silence

Figure 4. StringScore: Characters used in the definition of Track Segments

ment. A upper-case "M" can be used to indicate absence of sound or *mute* while running the position pointer in the motive. Finally, the segment descriptor can append one or more *sustain* characters indicating that the last sound must be maintained. The equal character (=) is used for this purpose. All character meaning are summarized in Figure 4. For a better understanding of segment descriptors, please follow the analysis of the example in subsection 3.6.

3.5 Musical Parameters

One of the main classes in the *EvMetamodel* and the responsible of its evolving quality is the *Dynamic Object*. Every parameter in the music section is a *Dynamic Object*, including environment parameters like dynamics or harmony as well as evolving motives. They can be defined in many ways ([16]), but in this context of *StringScore*, they are defined by using strings [Lines 6,15-18 in Figure 5] matching the timings of the rest of the section, including tracks. The category of the parameter is declared by a preceding keyword label. Depending on the expected type of value, several models of parameter string are defined, as explained below.

3.5.1 Symbolic Parameters

The string is parsed into positioned symbols. Every substring delimited by spaces, is considered a symbol located at the time position of its first character. The semantics of the symbols depend on the parameter type. *Dynamics* is a parameter example of this type [Line 12 in Figure 7] where symbols as *pp* (*pianissimo*) or *mf* (*mezzo forte*) are used. As an example the given string:

```
"pp mf fff mp"
```

is parsed into a *Status Change* dynamic object with the following pairs

```
-> (0 :pp) (5 :mf) (11 :fff) (16 :mp)
```

3.5.2 Numeric Parameters

When the expected value is a number, the parsed symbols are usually numbers. Some especial symbols are allowed like *hairpins*: "<" represents a linear crescendo, ">" a linear diminuendo, and "/" for the logarithmic versions.

```

01 (define-string-score-section
02 :name "museccion" :resolution 1/4
03 ;; thematic materials: motives
04 :ma (make-motive :pitch '(0 2 4 5) "+-+ i-1- +--+ +--+ *...")
05 :mb (make-motive :pitch '(0 7 3) "...*...*...")
06 :mc (op #'densify (pa :b) (op #'pitch (op #'list (li i 0 -5) (li i 3 24))))
07 ;; harmony definitions: new pcs types and maps for scale and chord
08 :pcs '(flamenco (0 4 10 13))
09 :%sc '(alidio bmixolidio cjonico dlocrio efrigio fmixolidio gdorico); by position
10 :%ch '(c cmaj :f fmin :d dmin :a aflamenco :e aflamenco); by keyword
11 ;; instrumentation: primary definition of the orchestra
12 :1inst :violin :1dk 's :1rg "f4" ;numeric prefix is the track number
13 :2inst :violin2 :2dk 'cb3 :2rg "c4"
14 ;; mastertrack 3---5---8---10---15---15---20---
15 :meter "4/4"
16 :tempo "120"
17 :sc "a b f a c d f 90 a a f e"
18 :ch "c"
19 ;; segment tracks
20 :1sg "a-----3-----R-----b3-----c-----aI-----A-----M-----"
21 :2sg "a-----a-----b3-----+3-----a4-----"
22 :2rg "-----c4-----+3-----4-----"
23 )

```

Figure 5. A *StringScore Section* as an example using some of the Representation Features. The rendered score is shown in Fig. 6

In addition, relative values can be used by using a sign (+ or -) prefix:

```

"23 +8 >+3 <24 100"
-> (0 23) (4 31) (10 (li i 34 24)) (18 (li i 24 100)) (24 100)

```

A special case of numeric parameter is the *Notenumber* type found in the *register* (*rg*) parameter [Lines 17,19,21 in Figure 7]. In this type, *Pitchnames*, *PitchclassNames* and relative numbers can be combined:

```

"e2 g2 +3 -12 a6 b c5"
-> (0 40) (6 43) (12 46) (16 34) (23 93) (27 95) (30 72)

```

3.5.3 Mapping Parameters

The parameter string can contain character symbols used as keys in a given map. The results of mapping the symbols is collected into a *Status Change* dynamic object. Two types of maps are accepted: lists indexed by keywords [Line 10 in Figure 5] and generic lists in which mapping is carried out by the position in the list [Line 11]. The special mapping character “.” is used to indicate the next element of the list. In addition, direct values can also be inserted in the string coexisting with the key characters [Line 13 in Figure 7].

The mapping approach allows the use of other *Dynamic Objects* in the mapped values, multiplying the possibilities of representation:

```

(mapcs "a b 23 d . h" (12 (li i 10 45) 67
23 49))
-> (0 12) (5 (li i 10 45)) (8 "23") (15 23) (19 49) (23 67)

```

3.6 An Example of StringScore Section (SSS)

Figure 5 shows the definition of a whole *StringScore Section*. The music information starts with the definition of thematic materials, in the form of motives. In lines 4 and 5 two static motives (*ma* and *mb*) are defined. In line 6, a new dynamic motive *mc* is defined by progressively expanding the pitches of motive *mb* in a growing interval.

Following, the harmonic materials are defined. A custom *PitchClassSet* (*pcs*) is defined in line 8 as a new type of chord called *flamenco*. Line 9 defines the map to be used for scales, as a simple list. The prefix % in the keyword (%*sc*) indicates that the parameter is a map. For improving the symbolic semantics, seven scales are defined in the

Figure 6. Notation rendered from the Example *StringScore Section* in Fig. 5

same order of the *pitchclass* names (a, b, c, d, e, f and g). Line 10 defines a map for chords in the keyword-form including two chords of the new *flamenco* type.

In line 12 some parameters for track 1 are defined. Their keywords names start with the associated track number. Three parameters are defined in this line: the instrument to be used (*inst*), the diatonic key (*dk*) to be used in the harmonization process, and the register (*rg*) or pitch reference for the tessiture of segments. Line 13 defines the same parameters for track 2. In this case, the diatonic key (*dk*) indicates to use chords in the harmonization, and to take the a reference pitch located a minor third (3 semitones) above the bass of the running chord. The diatonic key for track 1 simply indicates to use the running scale for harmonization.

Lines 15 and 16 define meter and tempo respectively. In parameter *tempo* an *accelerandi* symbol from 120 bpm to 150 bpm is written at bar 11. The harmonic progression of the section is indicated in lines 17 and 18 with the definition of parameters *scale* (*sc*) and *chord* (*ch*). In this example all key characters has been chosen to have the semantic meaning of the root pitchclass.

The segment arrangement (*sg*) is shown in lines 20 and 21, for tracks 1 and 2 respectively. Track 1 starts with motive *ma*. At bar 4 the motive is transposed 3 diatonic steps and in bar 6 the retrograded version is played until bar 8, when the sound is sustained for 3 beats. After some bars of silence the inversion of motive *ma* is played from bar 14. At bar 18, the augmentation of this inversion is reproduced until bar 22 where the sound is sustained.

Track 2 starts at bar 6 also with motive *ma*. At bar 9, motive *mb* is played 3 diatonic steps higher. The reference register (line 22) is incremented in 3 semitones at bar 11 so the segment ends with a pitch elevation. Dynamic motive *mc* is played at bar 12 and then repeated at bar 14, a fourth higher when track 1 plays again. A re-exposition of motive

```

01 (define-string-score-section
02 :name "mysection" :resolution 1/4
03 :ma (make-motive :pitch '(0 0 -1 -4) ",,+ -+-+ -... -...")
04 :mn (make-motive :pitch '(0) "+- -... -...")
05 :pcs '(:m4 (0 3 5 7) :mb6 (0 3 7 8) :d (0 3 6) )
06 :%ch '(:c cm4 :b g7b9/b :a abmaj :x g7/b :y g7 :z cmb6 :u ab/c )
07 :1in :violin1 :1dk 'c :1rg "g4"
08 :2in :violin2 :2dk 'c :2rg "g4"
09 :3in :viola1 :3dk 'c :3rg "g3"
10 :4in :cello1 :4dk 'cb :4rg "c3"
11 :meter "2/4"
12 :dy "ff" p mf f ff p "
13 :ch "cm bd cmb6 g b b c x c x c a g b0 g u b0 g cm"
14 ;; "0 1 2
15 ;; "1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 1 2 3 4 5 "
16 :1sg "a--1--== a--== +--a--n n== a--a--n "
17 :1rg "g4 f5 g5 c5 g5 ab4 a--n a--n "
18 :2sg "a--1--== a1--c--== +--n n== a--n a--n "
19 :2rg "g4 a4 g4 c4 g4 d4 a--n a--n "
20 :3sg "a--1--== a--aI--n n== a--n a--n "
21 :3rg "g3 g4 e4 g3 a3 a--n "
22 :4sg "a_3_1_6--== n== n--n--a--n n== a_1-- a--n "
23 )

```

Figure 7. StringScore Code as the Analysis of the beginning of Beethoven’s 5th Symphony

ma at bar 17 is interrupted at the fourth beat of bar 18 and retaken at bar 19, when track 1 is muted. Track 2 ends again with motive *ma* and a sustained chord at bar 22.

The *StringScore Section* shown in Figure 5 has been composed specifically as an illustrative example of the music representation and the use of *segments*. The rendered score is shown in Figure 6. In just 15 lines of code, 22 bars of two-part music has been described from a high level of music abstraction without loosing any degree of control of the composition.

4. STRINGSCORE ANALYSIS OF BEETHOVEN’S FIFTH

If last example demonstrates the compactness of *StringScore*, the example shown in this section overcomes the previous one. The challenge of this section is to validate *StringScore* by the analysis and re-composition of a classical piece. The beginning of Beethoven’s Fifth Symphony was chosen for this experiment, because of its clear motivic structure, its popularity, and its four-parts texture.

Figure 7 shows the analysis of the first 35 bars in an arrangement for string quartet. The entire section is composed by using only one motive *a*, defined in line 3. The second definition *n* in line 4 allows the use of a sustained note.

Unlike the previous example (Figure 5), in which a harmony based on scales was used, in this example a chord-based harmony has been chosen. Lines 5 and 6 define the chords to be used in Line 13.

Lines 7-10 defines the instrumental parts of the arrangement. For example the first instrument, *violin1* is instructed to use chords (:1dk 'c) for its symbolic pitches and a default tessitura of *g4*. An additional indication is given to the cello part. A value of 'cb for its *diatonic key*, indicates to use the bass of the chord as reference.

The variations in time of meter, dynamics and harmony are indicated in Lines 11, 12 and 13 respectively. A measure ruler is included as comment lines (14-15) to facilitate the positioning in time.

The motive distribution of the composition is analyzed in lines 16-22. All parts start in *fortissimo* with the main

Figure 8. Beginning of Beethoven’s 5th Symphony as rendered from *StringScore* in Fig. 7

motive *a*, and repeat it at bar 3, one diatonic step below. *Viola* plays again the motive in *piano* at pitch *g4* which is answered consecutively by *violin2* and *violin1* at pitches of *a4* and *f5* respectively. *Cello* plays the bass of the chord *Cmb6*. The same scheme is repeated at bar 11 now in the harmony of the dominant (*G7b9/B*). This time the motive is pitch-compressed in *violin2*.

At bar 15 the motive is played by both violins. By comparing with the score rendered in Figure 8 you can observe that this time, the main motive *a* is harmonized into three pitches because Pitchclass *F* is now available in the dominant chord. *Viola* answers with the inversion of the motive (segment “aI-”) and *cello* keeps playing the bass note of the chord. The sequence is repeated towards the semi-cadence at bar 21 where the major chords *Ab* and *G* are played.

The second musical phrase starts at bar 24, again in *ff* with the main motive in all voices, and follows deploying the *dominant* chord downwards by using the main motive across each voice. This arpeggiated deployment is repeated at bar 31.

The analysis described above can be easily followed in the *StringScore* representation shown in Figure 7. In a few text lines, 35 measures of the four-parts music section have been represented. The re-composition of the music section from the analysis is shown in Figure 8. As a re-

Figure 9. Structure of the *Computer Music Cloud* used in the *StringScore in the Cloud* Application

sult, *StringScore* text in Figure 23 not only represents accurately the music section but it also keeps the semantics and the knowledge of the composition model, thus allowing the introduction of changes from a higher level of abstraction. The experiment described in this subsection constitutes a reliable validation of the proposed representation.

5. STRINGSCORE IN THE CLOUD

One of the benefits of textual representations is its ability to be integrated in the Web. In this section, the implementation of the Web application *StringScore in the Cloud* is described. Based in the Computer Music Cloud (CMC) paradigm [17], this application provides a creative tool for music composition using the *StringScore* model described above.

5.1 CMC Design

The CMC offers a whole framework for the development of Computer Music applications in the Cloud. The implementation is carried out by joining several specialized music services into a cloud. The CMC consist of different types of services: input, storage, development, agents and output services. They all share the same music representation and service protocol (*MusicJSON* [13]).

Figure 9 shows the structure of the proposed CMC for the application. The score is written in a text file stored in a standard web service. A Web application allows the edition of such text files, manages users and sessions, and calls other CMC services to perform the development of the section, by sending the *StringScore* text inside a *MusicJSON* request.

When the music is developed by the *StringScore Developer* into a score-level *MusicJSON* format, it is ready to be rendered. The appropriated output service is then requested and its output is fed back to the web application to be shown.

As a novelty in this CMC implementation, *Dropbox*² have been chosen as storage service. This approach delegates storage and ownership control to this reliable service. Other services like *GoogleDocs*³ have been considered

² <http://www.dropbox.com>

³ <http://docs.google.com>

Figure 10. Screen Capture of the prototyped editor for *StringScore in the Cloud*

and tested, but *Dropbox* is preferred because of its simplicity, automatic synchronization capabilities, and a more efficient management of plain text files.

5.2 CMC Client

The CMC client in this prototype has been developed over *TextDrop*⁴, an on-line text editor for *Dropbox*. Figure 10 shows a screen capture of the editor.

The text font chosen for the editor is monospace and a grid has been drawn in the text area in order to facilitate time alignment in *StringScore*. Four dedicated buttons have been added to the control bar for *StringScore* rendering. When they are pressed, a *MusicJSON* request is sent to the *Music Developer* service, and then to the corresponding output service: MIDI, Audio, Score, or *MusicJSON*. The *Output* services employed in this CMC were described in [17] and [13] as well as their communication protocol.

The *StringScore Developer* Service is the main device of this application. It is implemented in LISP over *EvMusic* and the *Ev Metamodel* [16] libraries. For web integration it make use of the *Hunchentoot*⁵ web server library. The CMC approach simplify the design and the implementation because of the re-utilization of generic music services. All output services, as well as the *StringScore Developer* service, are reusable. They have been installed in virtual machines inside a dedicated Cloud Computing architecture. The use of both *Dropbox* as storage service and *TextDrop* as the basic editor, provide the management of users and personal storage for the compositions.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces *StringScore*, a text-based and compact representation for music composition that facilitates the arrangement of motivic elements in *time*, with a high degree of independent control of musical form, harmony and texture.

What makes this text-based proposal unique is its visual approach. The text character has been taken as the unit of the dimension *time*, so the position of each character in

⁴ <http://blog.textdropapp.com>

⁵ <http://weitz.de/hunchentoot/>

the text is relevant. The representation provides a visual feedback of the arrangement of musical elements in *time*.

StringScore supports the motive-based composition in a visual text format. The composition model described by Schoenberg [15] has been expanded by incorporating dynamic parameters and dynamic motives, the development of *Symbolic Pitch*, and the use of motive segments as composition blocks. Three different composition examples have been described in this paper showing the maturation of the proposal.

Several levels of use have been described for *StringScore*, ranging from the definition of articulated rhythms, the sequencing of motive segments in instrumental tracks, the description of dynamic parameters both discrete and continuous, as well as the complete definition of musical sections in a compact, and musically semantic format.

The representativity of *StringScore* for motive-based composition has been validated under the approach of Musical Analysis, by re-composing the beginning of *Beethoven's Fifth Symphony* from its analysis in *StringScore* format. As a result, *StringScore* has represented accurately the score while maintaining the semantics and the knowledge of the composition model.

Finally, the web application *StringScore in the Cloud* has been introduced as the implementation of the composition model underneath Representation *StringScore*. The application is developed as a *Computer Music Cloud* (CMC) [17] benefiting from the features of the CMC approach like the reutilization of existing music services. As a novelty, this application integrates some General Purpose services into the CMC. In this application *Dropbox* is used as storage service. The *StringScore in the Cloud* application not only constitutes the proof of concept of *StringScore* in the Web environment, but it is a valuable tool for composing music on-line with the creative possibilities provided by this high-level of semantic representation.

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